

Assess The Impact of Micro Credit Regarding Women Empowerment: A Case Study of Slum Dwellers in Quetta, Balochistan

Journal of Quranic
and Social Studies
156-167

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Volume:3, Issue:2, 2023

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.

www.jqss.org

ISSN: E/ 2790-5640

ISSN: P/ 2790-5632

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Abstract

Present study was attempted the socio-economic and socio-psychological impacts of micro credit scheme regarding women empowerment in slum dwellers of Quetta city. Current research was mainly qualitative by nature. Multiple interactive sessions were held to grasp on the topic and gather information. Present study was conducted from April to June 2019-20, by using semi structured questionnaire. Focused group discussion, personal interview and participatory rural appraisal (PRA) techniques were applied. 45 females as a sample size were taken from study area. Due to the diverse socio-economic and socio-cultural dynamics of province the female enumerators were hired. In order to better assess changes both in economic and social life of targeted women, current study was developed six indicators. Based on the findings of focus group discussions and in-depth interviews with respondents the study was completed and followed by drawing conclusion and suggesting recommendation for future replication of project in the province. Any empowerment effort is well executed when it includes monetary benefits. Therefore, it was recommended that the social mobilization packages with regard to women empowerment should be promoted so as to enhance the socio-economic conditions of female through the various micro credit projects.

Keywords: Micro-credit; Women empowerment; Quetta; participatory rural appraisal; indicators

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